

Sustaining Respectful Maternity Care in Health Facilities of Rwanda

Key Messages

- Respectful maternity care enhances positive birth outcomes and childbirth experiences, and mitigates intrapartum mistreatment.
- Compared to the past, Rwanda has taken notable steps to improve respectful maternity care. However, more efforts are still needed to fully meet the standard of comprehensive, high-quality respectful maternity care.
- The study identifies five strategies to maintain and promote respectful maternity care, which include providing women-centered care, ensuring an adequate environment around childbirth, preserving and upholding community trust towards maternity services, enhancing professionalism, and strengthening supportive leadership.

Introduction

Childbirth, a significant human experience, necessitates respect. The World Health Organization (WHO) in 2018 stated the need to ensure a positive and pleasant delivery experience to every woman, being treated with utmost respect and dignity.¹ Lack of Respectful Maternity Care (RMC) contributes to maternal and neonatal morbidity and mortality, and is a violation of the rights of women and newborns.

The absence of abuse does not equate to RMC. Women and newborns can experience a blend of both positive RMC practices and mistreatment.² It is essential to proactively advocate for RMC while simultaneously making efforts to diminish mistreatment. In addition, respectful actions must be identified in a local context. Past studies on RMC in Rwanda have focused mainly on negative experiences.^{3,4}

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4. Rosen HE, Lynam PF, Carr C, Reis V, Ricca J, Bazant ES, Bartlett LA. Direct observation of respectful maternity care in five countries: a cross-sectional study of health facilities in East and Southern Africa. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*. 2015 Dec;15(1):1-1.

This policy brief presents strategies to facilitate and sustain RMC in Rwanda, developed from a study that assessed and explored RMC in health facilities of the Eastern Province of Rwanda.^{5,6,7,8}

Methodology

The study was conducted in five hospitals in the Eastern Province of Rwanda and involved 610 women who recently gave birth (surveys); 30 In-Depth Interviews (IDIs) for subset women who reported being respected; 10 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) involving midwives and nurses; 10 IDIs for physicians; and 10 IDIs for maternity unit managers. During validation, 10 stakeholders/experts in RMC participated.

Findings

The majority (70.2%) reported experiencing RMC. The most acclaimed RMC items (over 90%) included allowance of food and fluid intake (98.5%), non-discrimination (96.2%), receipt of necessary services (96.1%), and privacy (91.3%) as elaborated in Figure 1.

The statistical analysis revealed an association between reported high RMC and marital status, occupation, and mode of delivery. In logistic analysis, delivery by caesarian section was particularly associated with high RMC. Mothers who reported experiencing all 15 RMC items were only 36 (5.9%).

Figure 1: Self-reported RMC items

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Five themes emerged from the data analysis of mixed data from the mothers, Health Care Providers (HCPs), and stakeholders corresponding to the following strategies:

To ensure these five strategies are effectively implemented, a logical framework is proposed (Figure 2). The framework maps out the necessary inputs, activities, outputs, and outcomes required to institutionalize RMC across health facilities in Rwanda. It serves as a practical tool for policymakers, program managers, and implementers to plan, coordinate, and evaluate RMC interventions in line with national priorities and WHO standards.

Figure 2: Proposed logical framework for RMC strategies implementation in Rwanda

Discussion

While 70.2% of women in this study reported experiencing some form of RMC, only 5.9% received all 15 components, highlighting critical gaps in the continuity of care. Across Rwanda, RMC delivery remains fragmented - high coverage of individual elements masks the reality that few women experience truly comprehensive, respectful care. These findings signal an urgent need for system-wide action.

Recommendations

Adoption of multi-faceted strategies can successfully reduce the mistreatment of women during maternity care and improve the RMC provision; interventions that go beyond a sole focus are more likely to bring meaningful changes.^{9,10}

To close the gaps and institutionalize RMC as a standard of care across all health facilities in Rwanda, in alignment with WHO guidelines, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. The Ministry of Health to intensify efforts to establish standard RMC practices in all health facilities across Rwanda.
2. The proposed strategies to be applied across multiple levels by including policymakers, health leaders, health facility managers, communities, and any other relevant actor.
3. The promotion and sustainability of RMC in Rwanda to be integrated into the broader health system and actively engage relevant stakeholders as outlined in Figure 2 (p. 3).

9. Dhakal P, Creedy DK, Gamble J, Newnham E, McInnes R. Educational interventions to promote respectful maternity care: A mixed methods systematic review. *Nurse education in practice*. 2022 Feb 23;103317.

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